

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of *l*-Histidine by Alkaline Ferricyanide

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A spectrophotometric kinetic study of oxidation of *l*-histidine by alkaline ferricyanide has been conducted. The reaction follows complex kinetics, showing first order dependence in both alkali and histidine and second order dependence in ferricyanide. The rate of oxidation has also been found to be inversely proportional to initial ferricyanide ion concentration. A specific negative effect of ferrocyanide has been observed. The salt effect is found to be positive and energy of activation has been evaluated as 10.1 ± 0.1 kcal. A suitable mechanism consistent with the experimental results has been proposed.

OXIDATION of a number of organic and inorganic substrates by ferricyanide has been studied¹⁻⁴.

Recently the kinetics of the oxidation of some α -amino acids by alkaline ferricyanide in presence of osmium(VIII) has been investigated⁵ and a strong catalytic influence of ferrocyanide has been observed. On the other hand, the oxidation of histidine in absence of osmium(VIII) showed a retarding influence of ferrocyanide ion. It was, therefore, interesting to investigate the detailed kinetics of oxidation of *l*-histidine by alkaline ferricyanide and formulate a suitable mechanism of oxidation.

Experimental

The solutions of *l*-histidine monohydrochloride were prepared from BDH sample of the reagent. All other solutions were prepared from BDH AnalaR reagents. Potassium ferrocyanide solutions were freshly prepared from a recrystallised reagent. Double distilled water was used throughout the investigation.

The rates were measured by determining the concentration of ferricyanide spectrophotometrically, using a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer. The measurements were made at 420 m μ and the concentration of ferricyanide was kept below $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Stoichiometry: The reaction mixture containing a known excess of ferricyanide over histidine was kept at 40° in presence of 0.2M NaOH for ten hrs. The results showed that the oxidation process can be represented by the following stoichiometric equation:

where R represents $HC=C-CH_2-$

The corresponding keto acid as the product was detected by spot tests⁶.

Results

The oxidation of histidine was studied at different concentrations of the reactants. The second order plots ($[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}]^{-1}$ vs time) yielded good straight lines (Fig. 1) for all kinetic runs. However, values of the pseudo second order rate constants (k_2) at various initial concentrations of ferricyanide (Table 1) show that the rate is inversely proportional to the initial ferricyanide ion concentration ($[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}]_0$).

Fig. 1. Second order rate plots ($[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}]^{-1}$ vs time) for different initial concentrations of ferricyanide at 35°. $[OH^-] = 0.2M$, $[Histidine] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}]_0 = 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5$ and $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ for A, B, C, D and E respectively.

The rates were found to be directly proportional to histidine concentration (Table 1). The values of $k_2/[Histidine]$ (at same concentration of ferricyanide) and $k_2[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}]_0/[Histidine]$ (Table 1)

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ AND $[\text{HISTIDINE}]$ ON THE RATE CONSTANTS AT 35° a

$10^4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ M	$10^3[\text{Histidine}]$ M	k_2 ($1.\text{mol}^{-1}\text{min}^{-1}$)	$k_2/[\text{Histidine}]$ ($1^2\text{mol}^{-2}\text{min}^{-1}$)	$k_2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]_0$ [Histidine] ($1\text{mol}^{-1}\text{min}^{-1}$)
3.0	4.0	2.02	505	0.152
3.5	4.0	1.66	415	0.145
4.0	4.0	1.50	375	0.150
4.5	4.0	1.53	392	0.149
5.0	4.0	1.16	290	0.145
5.0	2.4	0.66	275	0.138
5.0	3.2	0.88	275	0.138
5.0	5.6	1.44	257	0.129
5.0	8.0	2.08	260	0.130

a $[\text{NaOH}] = 0.2M$

were found to be reasonably constant. However, slight deviation was observed in these values from the others at higher concentrations of histidine. Dependence of the rate on $[\text{OH}^-]$ was also of first order at low NaOH concentrations while at higher alkali concentration, the order in $[\text{OH}^-]$ showed a slight increase (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Plot of k_2 (pseudo second order rate constant) vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ at 35°, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ and $[\text{Histidine}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}M$.

The values of the rate constants (k_2) in presence of different concentrations of ferrocyanide and sodium perchlorate (salt) are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ AND $[\text{NaClO}_4]$ ON THE RATE CONSTANTS AT 35° a

$10^4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ M	k_2 $1.\text{mol}^{-1}\text{min}^{-1}$	$[\text{NaClO}_4]$ M	k_2 $1.\text{mol}^{-1}\text{min}^{-1}$
None	1.16	None	1.16
1.0	0.63	0.20	1.55
2.0	0.44	0.40	2.11
3.0	0.36	0.60	2.88
4.0	0.31	0.80	3.55
5.0	0.27	—	—

a $[\text{Histidine}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.2M$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}M$.

Addition of ferrocyanide ion was found to retard the reaction rate, while sodium perchlorate had a positive influence on the rate of oxidation.

The measurements were made at 35, 40, 45 and 50° and the energy of activation calculated from Arrhenius plot was obtained as 10.1 ± 0.1 k. cal.

Discussion

The first order dependence on the alkali at low concentration of NaOH suggests that the effective species of histidine during the oxidation is the $(\text{histidine})^-$. The second order dependence on ferricyanide concentration implies that two molecules of ferricyanide are reacting in one or two steps. Furthermore, the inhibition by ferrocyanide suggests that at least one kinetically significant step involving the ferricyanide is reversible.

The iron(II) complexes⁷ of the amino acids and histidine-ferrocyanide complexes⁸ are mentioned in the literature. The {amino acid-ferrocyanide} complexes in alkaline media have also been detected⁹ spectrophotometrically. Similar results were obtained for the {histidine-ferro.} complex.

The mechanism consistent with these conclusions and also consistent with the other results listed above may be suggested as follows :

Applying the steady state conditions with respect to (X_T) and $(\text{His})^-$, the rate law equation is obtained as,

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = \frac{2k_1k_2k_4[\text{Histidine}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Fey}]^2}{\{k_2k_4[\text{Fey}]^2 + k_3k_3[\text{Foy}]^2 + k_3k_4[\text{Fey}][\text{Foy}] + \{k_1k_2[\text{Foy}] + k_1k_4[\text{Fey}]\}} \dots (5)$$

where $[\text{Fey}]$ and $[\text{Foy}]$ represents $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}]$ respectively.

As the concentration of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ as well as of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ is of the order of 10^{-4} and also k_1 is very large, the second order terms of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ in the denominator of the rate law equation (5) would be very small, and thus can be neglected in comparison with the first order terms

of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$. The rate law thus reduces to,

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = \frac{2k_1 k_2 k_4 [\text{Histidine}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Fey}]^2}{k_1 k^2 [\text{Foy}] + k_1 k_4 [\text{Fey}]} \quad \dots (6)$$

Now assuming $k_2 \approx k_4$,

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = \frac{2k_1 k_2 [\text{Histidine}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Fey}]^2}{k_1 [\text{Fey}]_0} \quad \dots (7)$$

where $[\text{Fey}]_0 = [\text{Fey}] + [\text{Foy}] = \text{initial concentration of ferricyanide}$.

The above rate law equation (7) predicts that the order in both histidine and alkali would be unity while that in ferricyanide would be two. The rate of oxidation is inversely proportional to the initial ferricyanide ion concentration. Our experimental results are in complete agreement with the above rate law equation (7). Such type of complex kinetics of the oxidation by ferricyanide is also reported in the literature^{9,10}.

Histidine is a tribasic acid and would give highly charged (histidine)²⁻ and (histidine)³⁻ ions at higher alkali concentrations whereby the order in alkali would show an increase which has also been observed (Fig. 2). As the slow stage (2) involves the interaction between similarly charged ions, a positive salt effect is expected which is also obtained experimentally.

The slight fall in the rate constants at higher concentrations of histidine (Table 1) may be due to slight decrease in the alkali concentration, as the solution of *l*-histidine monohydrochloride was used and the extra amount of alkali was not added to neutralise the acid present in the reaction mixture while studying the effect of histidine on the rate of the reaction. However, when runs involve the same concentration of histidine reasonably constant values of the rate constants have been obtained.

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